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Research Article

**IMPACT OF OBESITY ON DIABETES CONTROL AND
CHOLESTEROL LEVELS - A RETROSPECTIVE STUDY****Dr. Umair Tahir, Dr. Uswah Haleem, Dr. Tayyaba Noor**
Rawalpindi Medical University**Article Received:** April 2020**Accepted:** May 2020**Published:** June 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: To observe the relationship between BMI and glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) and hypercholesterolemia in the diabetic population.

Methods: A retrospective analysis of 809 patients was carried out at the Endocrinology department of Benazir Bhutto Hospital, Rawalpindi for one year duration from March 2019 to March 2020. A relationship between BMI and hypercholesterolemia and HbA1c was observed. Gender, BMI, HbA1c and cholesterol have been reported. BMI was divided into six classes: Underweight, Normal, Overweight, Obesity Class 1, and Obesity Class 2 and Obesity Class 3. HbA1c were classified as controlled or uncontrolled. Cholesterol was taken as control and without control.

Results: Of the 809 BMI patients, 23 were underweight, 210 were normal, 268 were overweight, and 308 were obese. In the group of obese people, class 201 was 201, class 2 86 and class 3 21. In the group of obese, class 1 was 50, class 2 was 35 years old, and class 3 - 10. Of 548 uncontrolled patients, 15 underweight, 147 normally, 173 overweight and 213 obese. Of this, class 1 was 151, class 2 was 51, and class 3 was 11. For cholesterol, 186 were controlled. Including, underweight was 8, normally 43, overweight 78 and obesity 57. in obesity class 1 was 38 years old, class 2 she was 17 and class 3 had 2 out of 623 uncontrolled people, 15 underweight, 167 normal, 190 overweight and 251 obese. , Class 1, 163, class 2, 69, and class 3, 19. This shows that out of 308 obese patients, 213 had uncontrolled HbA1c and 251 had uncontrolled cholesterol levels.

Conclusion: This study shows that high BMI is associated with poor glycemic and cholesterol control.

Key words: diabetes, obesity, HbA1c, hypercholesterolemia.

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INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes is a very common metabolic disease. Originally it was like a disease of wealth. A presence in third world countries, however, contradicts this theory¹⁻³. It has been established that both the poor and the rich can be equally affected, and lifestyle change is an important key to controlling it. Frequent observation of patients with type 2 diabetes is whether they are overweight or obese⁴⁻⁵. Type 2 pathology suggests that weight gain causes a proportional increase in endogenous insulin resistance. There are many other related factors, but increasing body mass index (BMI) is one of the most important factors⁶⁻⁷. Obesity leads to poor diabetes control. Control can be appropriately measured with glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c). High blood sugar causes irreversible glycosylation of hemoglobin during the lifetime of red blood cells⁸. Therefore, HbA1c shows the approximate average control over the last 3 months. In the literature, the burden of overweight and obese patients with diabetes and their effect on HbA1c has not been adequately documented. In our conditions, this documentation is much smaller. This relationship between obesity and diabetes has not been well documented in our region, especially regarding the various classes of obesity and their gender distribution⁹⁻¹⁰. Diabetes causes dyslipidemia. It affects in elevation of total cholesterol, triglycerides and low density lipoproteins. Lowers high density lipoproteins with beneficial effects. These guidelines have been approved in various guidelines to identify risk factors for coronary artery disease. This has been established in Pakistan, especially when total cholesterol is controlled only for economic reasons, but it has not been properly documented. Diabetes increases the risk of many complications that can affect the quality of life. All of them result in increased atherogenicity. Our goal in this study was to define the relationship between BMI and glycan hemoglobin (HbA1c) and hypercholesterolemia in our center. It will help us determine the load in various BMI groups and make local decisions regarding the intensification of treatment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A retrospective analysis of 809 patients was performed at the Endocrinology department Benazir Bhutto Hospital, Rawalpindi for one year duration from March 2019 to March 2020. According to BMI, the association of hypercholesterolemia and obesity with HbA1c was observed. Sex, BMI, HbA1c and cholesterol were recorded in all patients. BMI is divided into six classes: Underweight, Normal, Overweight, Obesity Class 1, and Obesity Class 2 and Obesity Class 3. HbA1c has been classified as controlled (less than 7%) and uncontrolled (over 7%) according to the guidelines of the American Diabetes Association. In accordance with ATP III guidelines, cholesterol level was adopted as controlled (less than 200 mg / dl) and uncontrolled (more than 200 mg / dl).

RESULTS:

Of the 809 patients, 2.8% were underweight, 26% were normal weight, 33.1% were overweight, and 38% were obese. In various obesity classes, class 1 was 24.8%, class 2 was 10.6%, and class 3 was 2.6%. Obesity was equal in both sexes, as was HbA1c and cholesterol control (Table 1, Graphs 3 and 4). Patients with controlled HbA1c were 32.26%. Of these, 0.98% were underweight, 7.8% normal body weight, and 11.8% overweight. There were 11.8% in this group of obese patients. In various obesity classes, class 1 was 6.2%, class 2 was 4.3%, and class 3 was 1.2%. Of 67.74% of patients with uncontrolled HbA1c, 1.9% were underweight, 18.2% were normal, overweight 22.1%, and obesity 26.3%. In various obesity classes, class 1 was 18.7%, class 2 was 6.3%, and class 3 was 1.4% (Table 2.1, 2.2, 2.3 and Chart 1). Of 809 patients, 23.99% had control cholesterol levels. Of these, 0.98% were underweight, normal weight was 5.3%, overweight 9.6%, and obesity 7.1%. In various obesity classes, class 1 was 4.7%, class 2 was 2.1%, and class 3 was 0.28%. Of the 77% with uncontrolled cholesterol, 1.9% were underweight, 20.6% were normal weight, 13.5% were overweight, and 31.1% were obese. In the various obesity classes, class 1 was 20.1%, class 2 was 8.5%, and class 3 was 2.4% (Table 3.1, 3.2, 3.3 and Chart 2).

CHART 1

CHART 2

CHART 3

CHART 4

Table 1: Sex differences according to BMI

	<18 U.W	18->25 Normal	25.1-30 Overweight	30.1-35 Class 1 Obesity	35.1-40 Class 2 Obesity	>40 Class 3 Obesity	Total
Male	12	82	144	120	52	12	422
Female	11	128	124	81	34	9	387

Table 2.1 Patients with Controlled HbA1c

	Female	Male	Total
Underweight	4	4	8
Normal	25	38	63
Overweight	64	31	95
Obesity Class 1	35	15	50
Obesity Class 2	16	19	35
Obesity Class 3	5	5	10

Table 2.2 HbA1c and BMI Association

	<18 U.W	18->25 Normal	25.1-30 Overweight	30.1-35 Class 1 Obesity	35.1-40 Class 2 Obesity	>40 Class 3 Obesity	Total
Controlled	8	63	95	50	35	10	261
Uncontrolled	15	147	173	151	51	11	548

Table 2.3 Patients with uncontrolled HbA1c

	Female	Male	Total
Underweight	8	7	15
Normal	54	93	147
Overweight	80	93	173
Obesity Class 1	85	66	151
Obesity Class 2	36	15	51
Obesity Class 3	7	4	11

Table 3.1 Patients with Controlled Cholesterol levels

	Female	Male	Total
Underweight	7	1	8
Normal	14	29	43
Overweight	37	41	78
Obesity Class 1	22	16	38
Obesity Class 2	6	11	17
Obesity Class 3	0	2	2

Table 3.2 Cholesterol & BMI Association

Cholesterol	<18 U.W	18->25 Normal	25.1-30 Overweight	30.1-35 Class 1 Obesity	35.1-40 Class 2 Obesity	>40 Class 3 Obesity	Total
Controlled	8	43	78	38	17	2	186
Uncontrolled	15	167	190	163	69	19	623

Table 3.3 Patients with Uncontrolled Cholesterol levels

	Female	Male	Total
Underweight	5	10	15
Normal	68	99	167
Overweight	107	83	190
Obesity Class 1	98	65	163
Obesity Class 2	46	23	69
Obesity Class 3	12	7	19

DISCUSSION:

Vázquez et al. Five Spanish datasets from observational studies have been published. The goal was to relate cardiovascular risk factors, HbA1c-assessed sugar controls, to patient age in different BMI groups¹¹. They documented that diabetes control is independent of BMI. However, this did not apply to other cardiovascular risk factors such as hypertension and hyper-triglyceridaemia. They recommended hypertension, dyslipidemia and close monitoring of obesity in young diabetic patients. These results differed from the results of our study. There were no significant gender differences in controlled or uncontrolled levels of HbA1c and total cholesterol in different BMI classes. However, most patients were in the obesity group with high BMI. The most common of these were patients with type 1 obesity. Then followed by overweight patients. Most had uncontrolled HbA1c (chart 1) and uncontrolled cholesterol (chart 2). This suggests a direct relationship between high BMI and poor HbA1c and cholesterol control in our population¹². Levine et al. A review article confirming a decrease in cholesterol level resulting in a reduction of cardiovascular events was published. They also identified important cholesterol levels and documented a greater chance of developing cardiovascular disease as levels increased over the years. The reduction effect has been documented in primary and secondary prevention. This work differed from us in many ways. First, we do not calculate the appropriate cardiovascular risk. Secondly, our study was retrospective and did not assess the increase in cholesterol and was not associated with increased heart load. However, we document that weak cholesterol is directly related to high BMI and poor diabetes control. Fasamande et al. A similar relationship between BMI and abdominal lubrication and atherogenic lipid profile was studied in patients with type 2 diabetes with hypertension and other diseases. They concluded that measuring lipid profile is not a reliable way to assess cardiovascular risk¹³⁻¹⁴. They also found that BMI was higher in the hypertensive group than in diabetic patients, and LDL cholesterol was the most common dyslipidemia. The number of patients included in the study was 278. This study differed from our work in many respects. 809 patients were included and only total cholesterol was measured in dyslipidemia, not all fragments. We control cholesterol in accordance with ATP III guidelines. It was found that the patients in the overweight group had primarily low cholesterol. Then obese patients. In the different classes of obesity, the Class 1 group had more patients, then Class 2 and 3. It was also observed that a significant number of patients were

in the normal BMI group with uncontrolled cholesterol¹⁵. Similar observations related to HbA1c control.

CONCLUSION:

This study shows that BMI was associated with poor glycemic and cholesterol control. It also showed that controlled glycemic control and controlled total cholesterol groups also have similar distribution in different BMI groups as poorly controlled groups. Groups of obesity 1 and BMI with overweight were highest in both controlled and uncontrolled patients. The total number of patients with poor control was significantly higher and there was no significant gender difference.

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